

Deliverable D14.2

Machine-readable Second Edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue

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Table of contents

1. Executive Summary	2
2. Contribution towards project objectives	3
Objective 1	3
Objective 2	4
Objective 3	4
Objective 4	5
3. Methods	6
3.1 Deliverable scope	6
3.2 Spreadsheet	6
3.3 Database	6
4. Description of work accomplished	7
4.1 Machine-readable EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue	7
4.1.1 Conversion of TRE Provider Survey results	7
4.1.2 Clustering of fields	7
4.1.3 Catalogue schema	8
4.2 Cross-work package discussions	8
5. Results	9
6. Discussion and Conclusions	13
7. Next steps	14
7.1 Elaboration of use cases	15
7.2 Maintenance, sustainability and governance	16
8. Impact	17
Appendix 1. Catalogue schema	18

1. Executive Summary

The EOSC-ENTRUST project aims to create a European Network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs). One task in this 3-year project is to establish a machine-readable TRE Provider catalogue, listing available TREs and their respective capabilities. Towards the end of the project, this *EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue* (short: *catalogue*) shall be made accessible as part of the EOSC Federation offering.

The catalogue will depend on service providers to populate it with detailed descriptions of their service capabilities to allow a comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps between environments. The public version of the catalogue will give potential users of these services a tool to map their secure processing environment requirements to the available solutions.

In this report, we describe the steps taken to convert the first edition of the catalogue (D13.3¹) to a functional database. This deliverable takes input from the second edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Inventory provided by the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Forum work package (WP11).

The chosen format for this version of the catalogue is a database that can be used as backend for services. In the future, it will be developed for more detailed and technically advanced versions that will serve multiple use cases. The final catalogue edition is scheduled to be delivered in autumn 2026.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	Yes
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	No

¹ Kallberg, M., Baxter, R., Kirschenmann, S., & Lehvälaiho, H. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D13.3 Machine-readable First Edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/14412490>

Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	No
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	No
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18)	No
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	No
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes ² principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15)	No
	5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
Objective 3 National funders and	1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	Yes

² Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes	2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).	No
	3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No
Objective 4 The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.	1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No
	2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).	No
	3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)	No

3. Methods

3.1 Deliverable scope

Deliverable D14.2 along with this report is the second version of the Machine-readable³ EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue. The first edition was published in November 2024⁴. It has a planned follow-up deliverable in the third and final year of the project in August 2026. The primary use case for the final edition is to have a comprehensive listing of exemplary TRE/SPEs in the EOSC offering – stating the respective capabilities, tooling, access mechanisms, etc. – to allow comparison of the environments and allow choosing the right environment for the right scenario.

The second edition of the Machine-readable EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue is primarily based on a TRE inventory provided by WP11. The inventory contains the condensed results obtained from the 2025 EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Survey⁵, conducted by WP11, as part of their task to perform an inventory & summary of current TRE Provider capabilities (MS11).

Based on information gathered in the inventory, the second version of the catalogue aims to build a functional database based on the survey answers. The final version of the catalogue will have an improved format, which will finally be published.

3.2 Database

The first edition of the machine-readable catalogue reported on in *Kallberg et al (2024)* was in a spreadsheet format, as this was the best solution during the initial phase. As a next step, the initial version has now been converted to a functional database. The database can be used as a backend source of information for multiple services. At this stage of the project, the database is built to run on CSC's Database-as-a-service platform.

³ Open Data Handbook definition for “machine-readable”:

<https://opendatahandbook.org/glossary/en/terms/machine-readable/>

⁴ Kallberg, M., Baxter, R., Kirschenmann, S., & Lehvälaiho, H. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D13.3 Machine-readable First Edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14412490>

⁵ Vihervalli, U. (2025). MS11: T4.4 Summary of updated TRE provider capabilities. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16960482>

4. Description of work accomplished

The main task was to build a functional database based on the first version of the machine-readable EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Catalogue. Collaboration with WP11 is important to ensure alignment between the strongly related TRE Survey & Inventory and the machine-readable catalogue.

4.1 Machine-readable EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue

4.1.1 Conversion of TRE Inventory results

The second version of the WP11 TRE Inventory was compiled based on the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Survey results and will be updated during the last year of the project. It was co-designed by the WP11 partner representatives, and also input from other ENTRUST WPs was invited. Whereas the first year survey was structured around the 5 Safes, the second iteration was now sectioned by themes, e.g. Functional Capabilities and Access & Accessibility. The invitation to participate in the survey was not only extended to partners within the projects, but also to interested providers outside of ENTRUST. The resulting TRE inventory dataset contained information on 25 TREs from 11 countries.

The survey included both multiple choice and free text response options. Since the survey structure was aligned with the First year version of the Machine-readable EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Catalogue, the data was already in a structure suitable for feeding it to the database in progress.

4.1.2 Database schema

The database schema has been developed based on the Catalogue schema that was developed as the first year version of the EOSC-ENTRUST machine readable TRE Provider Catalogue and documented in Deliverable 13.3⁶. During the development of the database schema, we identified commonalities in order to make the database functional for multiple use-cases for the future development of the TRE Provider Catalogue. When developing the database schema, the columns of the TRE Provider catalogue were divided into 28 different tables that are linked together into the database main table via internal id's. The main reason for having multiple tables linked in the database is that this will enable handling of larger datasets and allow for better optimisation for multiple use-cases, for example restricting the visible columns to only certain ones for a public version of the catalogue.

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/14412490>

As the second version of the WP11 TRE Inventory has further iterated the survey from the previous catalogue schema, the database schema was altered to match the latest survey structure.

The database schema is documented in [Appendix 1](#).

4.1.3 Database

The database is built from the schema described in the previous chapter. The current version is built on a PostgreSQL⁷ database and is running on CSC's DataBase-As-A-Service (DBAAS) Pukki⁸-platform. The PostgreSQL format was chosen because it is a widely used open-source database engine and it supports multiple data types.

Pukki – DataBase as a Service-platform was chosen because it offers easy and effortless setup of the database and it can be managed as a self-service. It is developed by CSC and is part of CSC's service portfolio for researchers.

Setting up the database in another service platform should be easy to facilitate and can be done, in case needed, e.g. in case the EOSC-catalogue would not be hosted at CSC and the database should be moved to a new service platform.

4.2 Cross-work package discussions

This deliverable is closely related to tasks and deliverables of other EOSC-ENTRUST work packages as well as further deliverables of the Architecture WP. As stated earlier, the results of the *Inventory & summary of updated TRE Provider capabilities* – a milestone for the Providers work package 11 – are directly fed into this catalogue. The second version of the TRE Provider Survey was aligned with the structure of the first edition of the machine-readable TRE Catalogue schematic that was described in deliverable 13.3.

The relationship between the TRE Inventory and the TRE Catalogue was also discussed in a designated breakout session at the 2nd EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements and Capabilities workshop in May 2025⁹. Whereas they are closely related, it was stated that one should also be mindful of the differences. For example, the TRE Inventory is more aimed at getting an overview of the organisational landscape, whereas the TRE catalogue could also include more technical details. The Inventory should be maintained by the

⁷ <https://www.postgresql.org/>

⁸ <https://research.csc.fi/service/pukki-database-as-a-service-dbaas/>

⁹ 2nd EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements and Capabilities Workshop. Zenodo. (2025).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15473397>

Provider Forum also after the project ending, whereas the TRE Provider Catalogue is intended to be part of the EOSC offering.

It was concluded that continuous cross-WP discussion is needed to define a process for alignment between Inventory, Catalogue and the Requirements Management Framework (Task 4.3 of WP11).

In addition to the workshop, representatives from other work packages are regularly taking part in the regular and task-specific Architecture WP meetings. This ensures a continuous information flow between the related WPs. This report was also reviewed by representatives from Drivers and Providers.

5. Results

The goal of the deliverable was to create the *Machine-readable Second Edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue* in database format. The catalogue is based on the data from TRE Provider forum (WP11) first and second year TRE surveys.

The database structure was based on the first version of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue schema. For the second year survey, the TRE Provider Forum made minor changes to the existing schema to fit the survey. These changes were also adopted for the catalogue database schema, so that the data can be entered with only a few minor conversions.

The schema of the database is described below.

Table 1

Field	Values	Provider survey question
tre_id	PID: "TRES" + running number filled to four digits	Unique ID for TRE
name	free-text	Name of the environment
host_org	free-text	Name of host organisation
ror_id_url	free-text	Organisation ROR
country_code	free-text	Organisation two-letter country code

self_description	Trusted Research Environment (TRE), Secure Processing Environment (SPE), Data Safe Haven, HPC, Remote access system, Other	Service self-description
self_description_comment	free-text	Service self-description additional information
gdpr_role	data processor, data controller, both	GDPR role of the organisation
service_zone	TRE/RAZ, TRE/SDZ, TRE/QMZ	TRE service zones present
service_dedication	sensitive data, multi-purpose	Is the environment available only for processing sensitive data use cases?
public_description_url	free-text	Public description of environment (URL)
public_benefit	Yes, No, N/A	Is the service available only for public benefit purposes?
self_service_user_login	Yes, No, N/A	Self-service user login
two_factor_auth	Yes, No, N/A	Two-factor authentication
single_sign_on	Yes, No, N/A	Single sign-on
access_mechanism_comments	free-text	Additional information on access mechanism
country_access_id	only national, other EU countries, other EEA countries, non-EU, other	From which countries can the environment be accessed?
country_access_comments	free-text	Country access additional information
pi_registration_id	only national, other EU countries, other EEA countries, non-EU, other	From what region can the PI be registered?
pi_registration_comments	free-text	PI registration additional information

member_registration_id	only national, other EU countries, other EEA countries, non-EU, other	From what region can non-PI project members be registered?
member_registration_comments	free-text	Member registration additional information
cloud_type_id	public, private, hybrid	Premise/private cloud, public cloud, or hybrid
data_type_inside	Plain text files, Document files, Spreadsheet files, Source code, Images, DICOM files, Binary data in proprietary format, Unrestricted, Other	Supported technical data types inside the environment
data_type_inside_comments	free-text	Supported technical data types inside the environment additional information
data_type_export	Plain text files, Document files, Spreadsheet files, Source code, Images, DICOM files, Binary data in proprietary format, Unrestricted, Other	Supported technical data types for export
data_type_export_comments	Free-text	Supported technical data types for export comments
iso27001_certification	yes, no, in progress	ISO27001 certification
security_audits	national, regional, organisational, other	Other security audits and certificates
security_audit_comments	free-text	Security audit additional information
tenancy_isolation	yes, no	Are project areas fully isolated from each other?
tenancy_isolation_comments	free-text	How are project areas isolated from each other?
security_access	multi-factor authentication, federated user accounts, individual identification,	Security measures against unauthorised access

	other	
security_access_comments	free-text	Security measures additional information
security_dataloss	data backup, snapshots, user guidelines, cybersecurity measures, other	Security measures for mitigating data loss
security_dataloss_comments	free-text	Security measures for mitigating data loss, additional information
security_misuse	Authorized access, Export encryptions, Sanctions, Certifications, User restrictions, User training, Other	Security measures for mitigating misuse by users
security_misuse_comments	free-text	Security measures for mitigating misuse by users, additional information
base_os_id	Windows, Linux, Rocky, Ubuntu, Redhat Enterprise, Unix, CentOS Stream, macOS, ChromeOS, Other	Standard base operating system
base_os_comments	free-text	Standard base operating system additional information
user_os_id	Windows, Linux, Rocky, Ubuntu, Redhat Enterprise, Unix, CentOS Stream, macOS, ChromeOS, Other	Operation systems available for users
User_os_comments	free-text	Operation systems available for users addition
hpc_access	Yes, No	Access to HPC in/through the environment
tooling	TensorFlow, PyTorch, Keras, Scikit, Custom-made analysis software, RStudio, Jupyter Notebooks, Other	Provided tooling

tooling_comments	free-text	Additional information on provided tooling
ai_support	Yes, No	Support for AI/machine learning
user_software_import	Yes, No	Are users allowed to import code/software/libraries?
user_import_size	Any, Limited	User import size
user_import_source	Clipboard, Unregulated network access, Network access regulated by TRE, Network access regulated by external entity, Other	User import data type
user_import_comment	free-text	User import data additional information
user_import_type	Any, Text only, Source code, Containers, Data, Explicitly no sensitive data	User import type
user_import_comments	free-text	Additional information on user import type
user_import_connection	Unregulated, Encrypted, Limited to stated internal addresses, Limited to any stated addresses, Other	User import connection
user_import_connection_comments	free-text	Additional information on user import connection
user_import_condition	No restrictions, Inputs are checked - automated, Inputs are checked - manual, Sampling - automated (some imports checked), Sampling - manual (some imports checked), No import by users	Conditions on users importing code/software/libraries
malicious_code_mitigation	Antivirus checks for all imports, Regular monitoring, Restrictions on	Measures against malicious code execution

	root access, Other	
malicious_code_mitigation_comments	free-text	Measures against malicious code execution additional information
public_discovery_service	Yes, No	Public discovery service for datasets available in this TRE
discovery_service_url	free-text	A link to the public discovery service
federated_queries	Yes, No	Does the service support federated queries?
federated_queries_comments	free-text	Additional information about supporting federated queries
external_data	Yes, No	Does the service support federated queries of metadata/data from external authorised users?
external_data_comments	free-text	Please provide details.
reference_architecture	SATRE, National reference architecture, Institutional reference architecture, EOSC ENTRUST blueprint, Other	Does the environment follow a specific reference architecture?
reference_architecture_comments	free-text	Additional information on reference architecture

6. Discussion and Conclusions

The second edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue lays a strong foundation for the final version. It facilitates comparative analysis of TRE capabilities and serves as a reference point for expanding the catalogue's scope. Moreover, it lists the first potential participants in a federated network.

The database format has been designed based on the TRE Provider surveys and developed to support multiple use-cases, with the aim that the format should be futureproof. We recognize that there will be future changes for the database content, but the current database structure should allow those changes to happen. This transition to a

dedicated database system will not only enhance data management but also improve functionality, such as enabling faster querying, more complex analytics, version control, and better integration with other systems within the EOSC ecosystem.

The data collection process highlighted the presence of gaps and inconsistencies in survey responses, which pose risks to the catalogue's overall completeness, accuracy, and reliability. Ensuring data quality therefore requires the systematic application of quality assurance measures that promote both consistency and standardisation. Potential methodological approaches include the implementation of controlled vocabularies and predefined input schemas to reduce variability, as well as the integration of automated validation and compliance checks prior to data ingestion. Collectively, these measures constitute a structured data quality assurance framework that is essential for safeguarding the methodological robustness and long-term utility of the catalogue.

Reinforcing cross-WP interactions will not only mitigate existing data gaps but also advance the development of sustained, interoperable relationships with TRE providers, thereby enabling continuous collaboration and systematic data exchange. These integrative efforts are critical to ensuring the long-term sustainability, methodological robustness, and evidentiary reliability of the catalogue, thereby consolidating its position as a trusted and authoritative component within the EOSC framework.

In addition to having the catalogue publicly available on the project website by the end of the project, a more detailed version could be made available to members of the TRE federation, providing information relevant to the members of the federation, but not suited for outsiders.

7. Next steps

The second version of the TRE provider catalogue is a functional database showing an updated snapshot collected from actual practitioners in the field. Looking back to the first year version of the deliverable, we have not yet been able to answer all the questions presented last time: Is it complete? How should it be maintained? How should it change?

Last year, we identified two next steps: to identify how the catalogue will be used; and to plan for wider dissemination and engagement with providers beyond the project consortium. In collaboration with Providers forum WP11, we have been able to align the TRE survey and catalogue and will continue this cross-WP alignment.

EOSC-ENTRUST will host the 2nd Evaluation & Adoption workshop in Bergen, Norway, on September 17-18, 2025. The workshop is organised by WP14 and will provide room for discussions and alignment between the different work packages. This will be important for moving forward with the project's goals, planning next steps, and working together on open

questions. The agenda also includes a presentation on the current state of the Machine-readable catalogue. This presentation will update the project participants on the status and will help to define steps for the final iteration.

7.1 Elaboration of use cases

The ultimate goal of EOSC-ENTRUST is to create a blueprint for a network where as much inter-TRE traffic as possible can be automated safely, securely and transparently. The key to enabling that will be the information recorded in the provider catalogue. For that, we must understand the use cases that the catalogue must support.

Our initial analysis has identified two principal use cases for the catalogue:

1. A public-facing, human-readable version targeting research users who might be looking to select a TRE provider for their next research project. The researcher personas identified in the EOSC-ENTRUST Training Package (D13.2¹⁰) are a good reference for this use case. This version of the catalogue needs to provide enough information for a researcher to make an informed choice of the TRE partner, but at the same time not reveal too much technical information for security reasons. It also needs to be human-readable, requiring descriptive information.
2. A "service-facing", machine-readable version designed for other TREs and services within the EOSC-ENTRUST network to interrogate the catalogue automatically. This version will be important in building the required trust network between TRE service providers and is essential when we start to look at federated analysis patterns across multiple TREs. To send a workflow or other query from one TRE to another, the sending TRE needs enough information about the capabilities, data and security arrangements at the remote TRE to be able to reason automatically and configure its query appropriately. To enable a TRE to handle a workflow or query sent to it from another TRE, the receiving TRE will need enough information to decide on the authenticity of the query, whether the originating user is pre-authorised to submit the query, and whether the query is a match for the receiving TRE's query processing environment.

In addition to the first two use cases identified earlier, we have identified one additional use case:

3. A closed human-readable version, where you can find more information about the TREs, but you need to be identified as a researcher and logged in with your account. This use case would serve the purpose of finding more detailed information about TREs that cannot be viewed publicly, for example for security reasons. This could be an extension to the first use case.

¹⁰ Deliverable D13.2 Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year one Blueprint & Interoperability Framework [in review].

In addition to use cases, it is also necessary to account for external fixed points or constraints, namely the external standards and information sources that the catalogue must incorporate. This consideration is particularly critical for enabling the automated reasoning envisioned in the second use case. Standardised terminology for TRE-related concepts is likely to emerge through initiatives such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health or the European Health Data Space, and EOSC-ENTRUST must remain aligned with these external standards to ensure interoperability across a broad ecosystem. An additional option for consideration is whether the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue should be developed as a specialisation of the EOSC Provider Catalogue – potentially framed as an EOSC Provider TRE profile. In this scenario, TRE resources onboarded via the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue into the EOSC Federation would be required to comply with EOSC Federation policies, while the TRE Provider Catalogue profile itself would need to remain consistent with the EOSC Profiles.

7.2 Maintenance, sustainability and governance

The ENTRUST project generates three key outputs that represent critical assets for the research community and must be sustained beyond the project's lifetime:

1. TRE Inventory – a structured overview of existing Trusted Research Environments, providing baseline knowledge on the TRE landscape.
2. Requirements Management Framework – a methodological framework for capturing, organising, and prioritising requirements across stakeholders.
3. TRE Catalogue – a standardised catalogue of TRE providers and their services, enabling discoverability and interoperability.

7.2.1 Interdependencies and Maintenance Processes

These three outputs are inherently interconnected. To ensure coherence and ongoing usability, a process must be established that defines how these assets will update one another in a coordinated manner. A possible process could be that the TRE Inventory informs the Requirements Management Framework, which in turn defines the specifications for the TRE Catalogue. Such a process should include versioning policies, update cycles, and clear governance mechanisms for monitoring consistency across the three outputs.

7.2.2. Sustainability Planning

A comprehensive sustainability plan is required to address the future of these outputs after the conclusion of the ENTRUST project. Critical questions include:

- Ownership and responsibility – Who will maintain the TRE Inventory, Requirements Management Framework, and Catalogue once the project ends?
- Funding mechanisms – Under which funding structures can long-term maintenance be guaranteed (e.g., through EOSC funding programmes, national initiatives, or community-driven governance)?
- Institutional hosting – Which organisation(s) will act as custodians of these resources to ensure their persistence and accessibility?

Without clear answers to these questions, there is a risk that the outputs will lose relevance over time, reducing their value to the broader community. WP12 will have a task next year to build a sustainability model for the provider EOSC-ENTRUST forum.

7.2.3 Ensuring a “Place to Live”

Each output requires a stable hosting environment where it can remain accessible, visible, and actively maintained. This may involve integration into existing EOSC infrastructures, alignment with international catalogues, or hosting under a dedicated governance body established for TRE-related resources. Long-term sustainability will depend on embedding these outputs within structures that have both technical stability and institutional support.

7.2.4 Data Updates and Integrity

For these resources to remain reliable, mechanisms must be established to ensure that data is kept up to date and accurate. A structured update process should be designed to guarantee that:

- Data used across multiple use-cases always reflects the most recent version.
- Updates are sourced from verified and trusted providers to safeguard data integrity.
- Change logs and provenance tracking are in place to ensure transparency of modifications.

This requires not only technical infrastructure for synchronisation and validation but also governance mechanisms for authorising data submissions.

7.2.5 Alignment with EOSC Federation

Finally, long-term sustainability of ENTRUST outputs depends on alignment with the evolving EOSC Federation. As EOSC continues to develop policies, profiles, and interoperability frameworks, the TRE Inventory, Requirements Management Framework, and TRE Catalogue must remain compliant. Such alignment will ensure that ENTRUST outputs are not isolated but embedded within the broader European research ecosystem, thereby increasing their impact, visibility, and long-term relevance.

8. Impact

The impact of this deliverable is significantly contributing to increased awareness of Trusted Research Environment (TRE) capabilities across Europe and promoting a more consistent understanding of their role among key stakeholders. Moreover, later iterations will lead researchers and data providers to a clear overview of the TREs available, thus assisting them in making informed choices. Additionally, it facilitates the establishment of a common framework for TRE providers, ensuring greater standardisation and interoperability across regions. This shared framework lays the groundwork for more effective collaboration and alignment and is essential for integrating TREs seamlessly into the broader European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem. Making the catalogue machine-readable is needed for data to be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) because it structures information for computers to process, search, and analyse automatically.

Notably, the European Commission, particularly DG SANTE, has recognized the work of EOSC-ENTRUST as pivotal to the development of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) directive. EOSC-ENTRUST has emerged as a major stakeholder in the EHDS initiative, with particular relevance to the efforts needed for setting up Secure Processing Environments (SPEs). This acknowledgement underscores the importance of EOSC-ENTRUST's contributions in shaping data governance frameworks and technical infrastructures essential for secure, cross-border health data sharing and research. It also highlights the strategic role of creating a European network of Trusted Research Environments for sensitive data in driving European interoperability in sensitive data research and in meeting the data security and privacy requirements that are crucial for advancing the EHDS objectives.

The second iteration of the EOSC-ENTRUST Machine-readable TRE Catalogue is not yet openly available. Once publicly available – which is the aim of the third version – the impact of the catalogue will naturally increase. It will provide a means for researchers as well as people involved in the development of SPEs and TREs to get a good overview of the capabilities of the various environments.

APPENDIX 1: Database schema

Draft image of database schema:

Database Schema:

-- Self-description

```
CREATE TABLE self_description (  
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,  
  description VARCHAR(50)  
);
```

```
INSERT INTO self_description VALUES(1, 'Trusted Research Environment (TRE)');
```

```
INSERT INTO self_description VALUES(2, 'Safe Processing Environment (SPE)');
```

```
INSERT INTO self_description VALUES(3, 'Data Safe Haven');
```

```
INSERT INTO self_description VALUES(4, 'HPC');
```

```
INSERT INTO self_description VALUES(5, 'Remote access system');
```

```
INSERT INTO self_description VALUES(6, 'Other');
```

-- GDPR roles

```
CREATE TABLE gdpr_role (  
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,  
  role VARCHAR(30)  
);
```

```
INSERT INTO gdpr_role VALUES (1, 'data processor');
```

```
INSERT INTO gdpr_role VALUES (2, 'data controller');
```

```
INSERT INTO gdpr_role VALUES (3, 'both');
```

-- Service dedications

```
CREATE TABLE service_dedication (  
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,  
  dedication VARCHAR(30)  
);
```

```
INSERT INTO service_dedication VALUES (1, 'sensitive data');
```

```
INSERT INTO service_dedication VALUES (2, 'multi-purpose');
```

-- Service zones

```
CREATE TABLE service_zone (  
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,  
  zone VARCHAR(10)  
);
```

```
INSERT INTO service_zone VALUES (1, 'TRE/RAZ');
```

```
INSERT INTO service_zone VALUES (2, 'TRE/SDZ');
```

```
INSERT INTO service_zone VALUES (3, 'TRE/QMZ');
```

```
-- Country access
CREATE TABLE country_access (
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,
  country_access_type VARCHAR(50)
);
INSERT INTO country_access VALUES (1, 'only national');
INSERT INTO country_access VALUES (2, 'other EU countries');
INSERT INTO country_access VALUES (3, 'other EEA countries');
INSERT INTO country_access VALUES (4, 'non-EU');
INSERT INTO country_access VALUES (5, 'other');

-- Cloud type
CREATE TABLE cloud_type (
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,
  cloud_type VARCHAR(10)
);
INSERT INTO cloud_type VALUES (1, 'public');
INSERT INTO cloud_type VALUES (2, 'private');
INSERT INTO cloud_type VALUES (3, 'hybrid');

-- Data types
CREATE TABLE data_type (
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,
  data_type VARCHAR(50)
);
INSERT INTO data_type VALUES (1, 'Plain text files');
INSERT INTO data_type VALUES (2, 'Document files');
INSERT INTO data_type VALUES (3, 'Spreadsheet files');
INSERT INTO data_type VALUES (4, 'Source code');
INSERT INTO data_type VALUES (5, 'Images');
INSERT INTO data_type VALUES (6, 'DICOM files');
INSERT INTO data_type VALUES (7, 'Binary data in proprietary format');
INSERT INTO data_type VALUES (8, 'Unrestricted');
INSERT INTO data_type VALUES (9, 'Other');

-- ISO27001 cert progress
```

```
CREATE TABLE iso27001_certification (  
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,  
  status VARCHAR(20)  
);  
INSERT INTO iso27001_certification VALUES (1, 'yes');  
INSERT INTO iso27001_certification VALUES (2, 'no');  
INSERT INTO iso27001_certification VALUES (3, 'in progress');  
  
-- Security audits  
CREATE TABLE security_audits (  
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,  
  audit VARCHAR(50)  
);  
INSERT INTO security_audits VALUES (1, 'national');  
INSERT INTO security_audits VALUES (2, 'regional');  
INSERT INTO security_audits VALUES (3, 'organisational');  
INSERT INTO security_audits VALUES (4, 'other');  
  
-- Measures against unauthorized access  
CREATE TABLE security_access (  
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,  
  security_access_method VARCHAR(50)  
);  
INSERT INTO security_access VALUES (1, 'multi-factor authentication');  
INSERT INTO security_access VALUES (2, 'federated user accounts');  
INSERT INTO security_access VALUES (3, 'individual identification');  
INSERT INTO security_access VALUES (4, 'other');  
  
-- Measures against data loss  
CREATE TABLE security_dataloss (  
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,  
  security_dataloss_method VARCHAR(50)  
);  
INSERT INTO security_dataloss VALUES (1, 'data backup');  
INSERT INTO security_dataloss VALUES (2, 'snapshots');  
INSERT INTO security_dataloss VALUES (3, 'user guidelines');  
INSERT INTO security_dataloss VALUES (4, 'cybersecurity measures');  
INSERT INTO security_dataloss VALUES (5, 'other');
```

```
-- Measures against misuse by users
CREATE TABLE security_misuse (
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,
  security_misuse_method VARCHAR(50)
);
INSERT INTO security_misuse VALUES (1, 'authorized access');
INSERT INTO security_misuse VALUES (2, 'export encryptions');
INSERT INTO security_misuse VALUES (3, 'sanctions');
INSERT INTO security_misuse VALUES (4, 'certifications');
INSERT INTO security_misuse VALUES (5, 'user restrictions');
INSERT INTO security_misuse VALUES (6, 'user training');
INSERT INTO security_misuse VALUES (7, 'other');
```

```
CREATE TABLE os (
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,
  operating_system VARCHAR(30)
);
INSERT INTO os VALUES (1, 'Windows');
INSERT INTO os VALUES (2, 'Linux');
INSERT INTO os VALUES (3, 'Rocky');
INSERT INTO os VALUES (4, 'Ubuntu');
INSERT INTO os VALUES (5, 'Redhat Enterprise');
INSERT INTO os VALUES (6, 'Unix');
INSERT INTO os VALUES (7, 'CentOS Stream');
INSERT INTO os VALUES (8, 'macOS');
INSERT INTO os VALUES (9, 'ChromeOS');
INSERT INTO os VALUES (10, 'Other');
```

```
-- Tooling provided
CREATE TABLE tooling (
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,
  tool VARCHAR(50)
);
INSERT INTO tooling VALUES (1, 'TensorFlow');
INSERT INTO tooling VALUES (2, 'PyTorch');
INSERT INTO tooling VALUES (3, 'Keras');
INSERT INTO tooling VALUES (4, 'Scikit');
```

```
INSERT INTO tooling VALUES (5, 'Custom-made analysis software');
INSERT INTO tooling VALUES (6, 'RStudio');
INSERT INTO tooling VALUES (7, 'Jupyter Notebooks');
INSERT INTO tooling VALUES (8, 'Other');

-- User import source
CREATE TABLE user_import_source (
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,
  source VARCHAR(50)
);
INSERT INTO user_import_source VALUES (1, 'Clipboard');
INSERT INTO user_import_source VALUES (2, 'Unregulated network access');
INSERT INTO user_import_source VALUES (3, 'Network access regulated by TRE');
INSERT INTO user_import_source VALUES (4, 'Network access regulated by external
entity');
INSERT INTO user_import_source VALUES (5, 'Other');

-- User import size
CREATE TABLE user_import_size (
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,
  size VARCHAR(20)
);
INSERT INTO user_import_size VALUES (1, 'Any');
INSERT INTO user_import_size VALUES (2, 'Limited');

-- User import type
CREATE TABLE user_import_type (
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,
  type VARCHAR(30)
);
INSERT INTO user_import_type VALUES (1, 'Any');
INSERT INTO user_import_type VALUES (2, 'Text only');
INSERT INTO user_import_type VALUES (3, 'Source code');
INSERT INTO user_import_type VALUES (4, 'Containers');
INSERT INTO user_import_type VALUES (5, 'Data');
INSERT INTO user_import_type VALUES (6, 'Explicitly no sensitive data');
```

```
-- User import connection
CREATE TABLE user_import_connection (
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,
  connection VARCHAR(50)
);
INSERT INTO user_import_connection VALUES (1, 'Unregulated');
INSERT INTO user_import_connection VALUES (2, 'Encrypted');
INSERT INTO user_import_connection VALUES (3, 'Limited to stated internal addresses');
INSERT INTO user_import_connection VALUES (4, 'Limited to any stated addresses');
INSERT INTO user_import_connection VALUES (5, 'Other');
```

```
-- User import conditions
CREATE TABLE user_import_condition (
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,
  condition VARCHAR(50)
);
INSERT INTO user_import_condition VALUES (1, 'No restrictions');
INSERT INTO user_import_condition VALUES (2, 'Inputs are checked - automated');
INSERT INTO user_import_condition VALUES (3, 'Inputs are checked - manual');
INSERT INTO user_import_condition VALUES (4, 'Sampling - automated (some imports checked)');
INSERT INTO user_import_condition VALUES (5, 'Sampling - manual (some imports checked)');
INSERT INTO user_import_condition VALUES (6, 'No import by users');
```

```
CREATE TABLE malicious_code_mitigation (
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,
  malicious_mitigation_method VARCHAR(50)
);
INSERT INTO malicious_code_mitigation VALUES (1, 'Antivirus checks for all imports');
INSERT INTO malicious_code_mitigation VALUES (2, 'Regular monitoring');
INSERT INTO malicious_code_mitigation VALUES (3, 'Restrictions on route access');
INSERT INTO malicious_code_mitigation VALUES (4, 'Other');
```

```
CREATE TABLE reference_architecture (
  id INT PRIMARY KEY,
  reference_architecture VARCHAR(50)
);
```

```
INSERT INTO reference_architecture VALUES (1, 'SATRE');
INSERT INTO reference_architecture VALUES (2, 'National reference architecture');
INSERT INTO reference_architecture VALUES (3, 'Institutional reference architecture');
INSERT INTO reference_architecture VALUES (4, 'EOSC ENTRUST blueprint');
INSERT INTO reference_architecture VALUES (5, 'Other');
```

```
CREATE TABLE tre_catalogue (
  -- Identity
  id SERIAL PRIMARY KEY,
  tre_id VARCHAR(10) NOT NULL,
  name VARCHAR(100) NOT NULL,

  -- Organization details
  host_org VARCHAR(100),
  ror_id_url VARCHAR(100),
  country_code VARCHAR(10),

  -- Functional capabilities
  self_description_comments VARCHAR(100),
  gdpr_role_id INT REFERENCES gdpr_role (id),
  service_dedication_id INT REFERENCES service_dedication (id),
  public_description_url VARCHAR(100),
  public_benefit BOOLEAN,
  -- Self-description and service zones are mapped to TREs in separate tables.

  -- Access mechanisms
  self_service_user_login BOOLEAN,
  two_factor_auth BOOLEAN,
  single_sign_on BOOLEAN,
  access_mechanism_comments VARCHAR(1000),

  -- (Inter)national access
  country_access_id INT REFERENCES country_access (id),
  country_access_comments VARCHAR(1000),
  pi_registration_id INT REFERENCES country_access (id),
  pi_registration_comments VARCHAR(1000),
  member_registration_id INT REFERENCES country_access (id),
  cloud_type_id INT REFERENCES cloud_type (id),

  -- Accepted data types
```

```
data_type_inside_comments VARCHAR(1000),
data_type_export_comments VARCHAR(1000),
-- Data types in environment are mapped to TRE in separate table.
-- Data types for export are mapped to TRE in separate table.

-- Auditing and security measures
iso27001_certification_id INT REFERENCES iso27001_certification (id),
other_security_id INT REFERENCES security_audits (id),
other_security_comments VARCHAR(1000),
tenancy_isolation BOOLEAN,
tenancy_isolation_comments VARCHAR(1000),

-- Security measures against unauthorized access, data loss and misuse mapped in
separate tables
security_access_comments VARCHAR(1000),
security_data_loss_comments VARCHAR(1000),
security_misuse_comments VARCHAR(1000),

-- Computing and analysis services
base_os_id INT REFERENCES os (id),
base_os_comments VARCHAR(100),
user_os_id INT REFERENCES os (id),
user_os_comments VARCHAR(100),
hpc_access BOOLEAN,
ai_support BOOLEAN,
tooling_id INT REFERENCES tooling (id),
tooling_comments VARCHAR(100),

-- User rights
user_software_import BOOLEAN,
user_import_size_id INT REFERENCES user_import_size (id),
-- User import source, type and connection, and malicious code mitigation methods
-- are mapped to TRE in separate tables
user_import_source_comments VARCHAR(1000),
user_import_type_comments VARCHAR(1000),
user_import_connection_comments VARCHAR(1000),
user_import_condition_id INT REFERENCES user_import_condition (id),
malicious_code_mitigation_comments VARCHAR(1000),

-- Data discovery
public_discovery_service BOOLEAN,
```

```
discovery_service_url VARCHAR(200),

-- Federated analysis
federated_queries BOOLEAN,
federated_queries_comments VARCHAR(1000),
external_data BOOLEAN,
external_data_comments VARCHAR(1000),

-- Architecture
reference_architecture_id INT REFERENCES reference_architecture (id),
reference_architecture_comments VARCHAR(1000)
);

-- Map between TREs and self-description options
CREATE TABLE map_self_description (
  tre_id INT REFERENCES tre_catalogue (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE,
  self_description_id INT REFERENCES self_description (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE,
  CONSTRAINT self_description_pk PRIMARY KEY (tre_id, self_description_id)
);

-- Map between TREs and service zones (defined below)
CREATE TABLE map_service_zones (
  tre_id INT REFERENCES tre_catalogue (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE,
  service_zone_id INT REFERENCES service_zone (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE,
  CONSTRAINT service_zone_pk PRIMARY KEY (tre_id, service_zone_id)
);

-- Map between TREs and measures against unauthorized access
CREATE TABLE map_security_access (
  tre_id INT REFERENCES tre_catalogue (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE,
  security_access_id INT REFERENCES security_access (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE,
  CONSTRAINT security_access_pk PRIMARY KEY (tre_id, security_access_id)
);

-- Map between TREs and measures against data loss
CREATE TABLE map_security_dataloss (
  tre_id INT REFERENCES tre_catalogue (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE,
  security_dataloss_id INT REFERENCES security_dataloss (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE,
  CONSTRAINT security_dataloss_pk PRIMARY KEY (tre_id, security_dataloss_id)
```

```
);

-- Map between TREs and measures against misuse by users
CREATE TABLE map_security_misuse (
  tre_id INT REFERENCES tre_catalogue (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE,
  security_misuse_id INT REFERENCES security_misuse (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE,
  CONSTRAINT security_misuse_pk PRIMARY KEY (tre_id, security_misuse_id)
);

-- Map between TREs and supported data types in environment
CREATE TABLE map_data_types_in_environment (
  tre_id INT REFERENCES tre_catalogue (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE,
  data_type_id INT REFERENCES data_type (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE,
  CONSTRAINT env_data_pk PRIMARY KEY (tre_id, data_type_id)
);

-- Map between TREs and supported data types for export
CREATE TABLE map_data_types_for_export (
  tre_id INT REFERENCES tre_catalogue (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE,
  data_type_id INT REFERENCES data_type (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE,
  CONSTRAINT export_data_pk PRIMARY KEY (tre_id, data_type_id)
);

-- Map between TREs and provided tooling
CREATE TABLE map_provided_tooling (
  tre_id INT REFERENCES tre_catalogue (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE,
  tooling_id INT REFERENCES tooling (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE,
  CONSTRAINT tooling_pk PRIMARY KEY (tre_id, tooling_id)
);

-- Map between TREs and user import sources
CREATE TABLE map_user_import_source (
  tre_id INT REFERENCES tre_catalogue (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE,
  source_id INT REFERENCES user_import_source (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE,
  CONSTRAINT user_source_pk PRIMARY KEY (tre_id, source_id)
);

-- Map between TREs and user import types
CREATE TABLE map_user_import_type (
  tre_id INT REFERENCES tre_catalogue (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE,
  type_id INT REFERENCES user_import_type (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE,
```

```
CONSTRAINT user_type_pk PRIMARY KEY (tre_id, type_id)
);

-- Map between TREs and user import sizes
CREATE TABLE map_user_import_size (
  tre_id INT REFERENCES tre_catalogue (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE,
  size_id INT REFERENCES user_import_size (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE,
  CONSTRAINT user_size_pk PRIMARY KEY (tre_id, size_id)
);

-- Map between TREs and user import connections
CREATE TABLE map_user_import_connection (
  tre_id INT REFERENCES tre_catalogue (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE,
  connection_id INT REFERENCES user_import_connection (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE,
  CONSTRAINT user_conn_pk PRIMARY KEY (tre_id, connection_id)
);

-- Map between TREs and malicious code mitigation methods
CREATE TABLE map_malicious_code_mitigation (
  tre_id INT REFERENCES tre_catalogue (id) ON UPDATE CASCADE ON DELETE CASCADE,
  malicious_code_mitigation_id INT REFERENCES malicious_code_mitigation (id) ON
UPDATE CASCADE,
  CONSTRAINT malicious_pk PRIMARY KEY (tre_id, malicious_code_mitigation_id)
);
```